

CULTUROLOGY

BREAD AND MILK METAPHORS IN HEBREW AND ENGLISH

Kigel T.

*Independent researcher of multilingualism (Project "Contrastive Analysis of English, Hebrew, and Russian Color Idioms")
Research interests - multilingualism, translation, teaching a second language and learning disabilities. Behazlaha-center, Petah-Tikva, Israel.
Orcid <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4136-4711>*

ABSTRACT

The study's aim was to do identification, analysis, classification, and comparison of English and Hebrew metaphors with the words bread and milk (MBM) as important ingredients of people's nutrition from a conceptual perspective. In the background of the English bread metaphor investigation, the milk metaphor has not been studied in two languages. The pilot and limited study corpus consist of 54 MBM (34 English and 20 Hebrew) including various forms of figurative language. Three tables (full, partial equivalents, and ethnocultural metaphors in every language) presented the work results. The investigation of English and Hebrew bread metaphors confirms their meta-conceptual status. Between numerous symbolic meanings, the key bread meaning is urgent physical person's needs, food, and life. Bread is a dichotomy symbol of wealth, plenty vis hunger, poverty, and in a modern extension, it symbolizes providing for the family and making money. Checking the diverse sources of English and Hebrew MBM proves that Tanakh and the New Testament are the eldest and most important sources of equivalent and ethnocultural ones. These metaphors featured philosophical meaning, and a high level of symbolization and conceptualization, while the late metaphors characterized practical, pragmatical, or even cynic connotations. Hebrew milk metaphors are the concept of pleasure and enjoyment, while English ones demonstrated the negative connotations and inferior status of milk in opposition to bread. Because of meaning diversity, ethnocultural metaphors cannot be organized in microsystems.

Keywords: English, Hebrew, bread, milk, metaphors, figurative language, Tanakh, Bible, lingua culture.

Introduction Eating and drinking as vital needs and universal primal and basic activities (Gannon, 2002) according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs, are the English, and Hebrew figurative language sources. Food as an engine and source of metaphorical meanings that permeates our life (Newman, 1997; Korthals, 2008; Kay, 2016), reflects the material and spiritual culture in the language.

Our global world requires interacting with different cultures together (Arasaratnam, 2013:48). Since the 20th-century phraseology research concludes that idioms are effective instruments of communication consequently, must acquire metaphoric competence in second language learning and teaching as a part of grammatical, textual sociolinguistic competence (Littlemore & Low, 2006:268). This is a reason to analyze and compare MBM in English and Hebrew, unrelated and structurally distant languages, which are Israel's most popular modern languages.

Figurative language uses words in a way that deviates from their conventionally accepted definitions in order to convey a more complicated meaning or heightened effect (Figure of speech), to model the language world picture, and to build a communication algorithm and a metaphor is a figure of speech in which a word or phrase literally denoting one kind of object or idea is used in place of another to suggest a likeness or analogy between them (Definition of Metaphor).

The paper is made in the framework of conceptualization (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980: 1), Cultural Linguistics explores the relationship between a language and the nonlinguistic cultural behavior of the people who

speak that language (Ethnolinguistics), and the multilingual approach (Pirainen, 2012:62).

The Lakoff theory claimed that conceptual metaphor is a universal process of human thinking reflected in language structures and leads to the interaction of two cognitive structures or areas: the source domain and the target domain with complicated links between them and the essence of metaphor is understanding and experiencing one kind of thing in terms of another.

Differences in metaphors are the result of natural, geographical, social, economic, and cultural differences as well as thinking modes.

In recent decades, a large number of linguistic research focuses on food concepts and food metaphors in different languages.

An important contribution to the intensive development of food metaphors in European and non-European studies contributed works on English (Pinnavaia, 2010, 2018); Russian (Pomarolli, 2021); Mandarin and Shanghainese (Ye, 2010), Portuguese (Monteiro, 2011; Martins, 2015; Moore, 2017). In addition, there are studies comparing food metaphors in English with another language e.g. French, German, and Spanish (Pinnavaia, 2015); Romanian (Ionesco, 2017); Croatian (Majic, 2017); Spanish (Negro, 2019), and Hebrew (Kigel, 2022b, furthering).

Bread is the focus of special studies e.g., in Russian, English, and Italian (Yurina, et al, 2017); Portuguese, Spanish, and Chinese (Monteiro et al., 2018). The bread biblical symbolism in Russian and Italian languages is a theme of the special paper (Yurina & Pomarolli, 2017).

The conclusions of six languages research prove that bread is archetypal or meta symbol of life, food-stuff, means of subsistence, prosperity, and abundance, material wealth, the unity of labor, and its results in opposition to poverty, and misery. Bread metaphors remind us that humans require a combination of physical and spiritual needs for well-being.

Bread baked from flour and rich in carbohydrates, combined in one product animal and vegetable energy has been an important part of many cultures' diets, a basic food product that is common almost all over the world since the dawn of human civilization (Bread). It exists in every home (especially in the West, Africa, and Asia - typically rice), and plays an essential role in both religious rituals and secular culture.

Milk is a white liquid food produced by the mammary glands of mammals and is the primary source of nutrition for breastfed human infants) before they are able to digest solid food (Van Winckel, et al., 2011). The English bread metaphor has been the focus of scholarly attention, but the milk metaphor has not been studied either in connection with the bread metaphor or specifically. The purpose of the study is to compare the metaphors of bread and milk in English and Hebrew as important ingredients in human nutrition from a conceptual point of view and to fill a gap in the research on milk metaphors in English and Hebrew.

The results should be relevant for comparative and contrastive linguistics, psycholinguistics, lexicology, cognitive linguistics, ethno-linguistics, and intercultural communication theory. In practice, the results and conclusions of the work can be useful in compiling new and reissuing existing explanatory and phraseological English-Hebrew dictionaries, paremiological and phraseological corpora, in textbooks, and can also be used in teaching English as a foreign language, L2 classes, interpretation, human and automatic translation.

Materials and Methods

The study's aim is to compare English and Hebrew bread and milk metaphors as the important ingredients of people's nutrition from a conceptual perspective.

The study corpus comprises 117 metaphors (74 English and 43 Hebrew) with the words *bread and milk*.

The figurative metaphors corpus is a pilot and as complete as the possible version that comprises idioms, set expressions, phraseological units, and paremiological units as proverbs, maxims, and sayings collected from electronic explanatory and phraseological dictionaries, token searches on the Internet.

Below is the applied procedure: definition of words, the gathering of metaphors in the above sources; listing the bread and milk metaphors of each language, and the equivalents emphasizing making comparing. Partial equivalents were noted and ethnocultural metaphors were analyzed separately for each language. The systematic results were presented in five tables upbuild on the classification principles of English and Hebrew metaphors with an edible plant (Kigel, 2022).

Then the national-cultural comments and conceptual metaphors were formulated.

3. Results

The study results are presented in Table 1 and Table 2. The study corpus is 54 metaphors (34 English and 20 Hebrew) with the words bread and milk. This is a pilot version that comprises idioms, set expressions, phraseological units, and paremiological units as proverbs, maxims, and sayings collected from electronic explanatory and phraseological dictionaries, and token searches on the Internet.

Below is the investigation procedure: definition of words, gathering of metaphors in the above sources, and classifying the bread and milk metaphors of each language. The full and partial equivalents were noted and ethnocultural metaphors were analyzed separately for each language and the systematic results were presented in three tables upbuild on the classification principles of English and Hebrew metaphors with an edible plant (Kigel, 2022b). Then the national-cultural comments and conceptual metaphors were formulated.

3. Results

The study results are presented in Table 1 and Table 2a and 2b.

Discussion

English and Hebrew Equivalents of Bread and Milk Metaphors

In total, the corpus consists of 54 metaphors -34 English and 20 Hebrew metaphors and besides the total number of English metaphors is more than Hebrew ones. In English, the number of bread metaphors is twice as much as milk ones (23 bread and 11 milk); in Hebrew their number is almost equal (11 bread and 9 milk), indicating the value of these products in the nutrition and language.

12 English and Hebrew metaphors are full or partial equivalents. A variety of metaphors sources are Roman satire, a French saying, and Greek myth (**Milky Way Galaxy**) but the main one is the Tanakh or Hebrew Bible (Carr, 2011), the canonical collection of ancient religious Hebrew writings by the Israelites, the main sacred book of Judaism, written in Hebrew and partially in Aramaic that was compiled in 450 BCE (Tov, 2008).

According to Pinnavaia (2010; 71-72), bread, the most idiomatically productive *le* and *me*, represents survival, livelihood, and has been the archetypal symbol of food since the beginnings of Western literature, and especially since the translations of the Bible into European languages

The investigation of English and Hebrew bread metaphors confirms the symbolic meaning of bread as an expression of the most urgent physical person's needs (bread and water- the most minimal meal, לחם צר ומים להץ (narrow bread and pressed water). Both physical and spiritual needs are vital for the human being (man does not live by bread alone, bread and circuses). Bread, as a metaphor, becomes a vehicle of transition from grain to spiritual life (Ledwon, 2017) that concord with other language studies spoken above.

Table 1.

English and Hebrew Equivalents of Bread and Milk Metaphors

Hebrew	English
לחם צר ומים להזין ישעיהו ל כ Narrow bread and pressed water A meager diet that is barely enough to sustain life	<i>bread and water</i> the most minimal meal
לא על הלחם לבדו יהיה אדם פסוק ג, דברים ה	<i>Man does not live by bread alone</i> people have spiritual as well as physical needs
לחם ושעשועים	<i>Bread and circuses</i> gaining public approval through superficial means such as diversion and distraction to hide fundamental flaws in society Jubanellis, a Roman poet and satirist 1st century BC
שלה לחמך על פני המים כי ברב הימים תמצאנו קהלת, פרק י"א	<i>Cast one's bread upon the waters</i> good behavior will be rewarded
בית לחם The Bread House פסוק י"ט, פרק ל"ה, ספר בראשית פסוק ז, פרק מ"ח	<i>Bethlehem</i> A city on Mount Hebron in the Judean Mountains, about 10 km south of Jerusalem
אם אין לחם תאכלו עוגות	<i>Let them eat cake</i> disregard or cynical attitude to the starving people Marie Antoinette phrase, the last Queen of France before the French revolution
ארץ זבת חלב ודבש במדבר, י"ג, כ"ז	<i>land of milk and honey</i> Land of Israel The modern extension: prosperity and abundance
שביל החלב	<i>The Milky Way</i> the galaxy that includes our Solar System
לא חלב, לא בשר No meat, no milk (without a clear character)	<i>Milk toast</i> a meek, submissive, or timid person
בכה על חלב שנשפך	<i>No use crying over spilled milk</i> (complain or regret something that has already happened if you can't change it)
למה לקנות פרה כשהחלב חינם	<i>Why buy a cow when (the) milk is free?</i>
לחם תמיד נופל על הצד המרוח בחמאה	<i>Bread always falls on the buttered side</i> things have a tendency to go completely wrong

The name of the city of לחם, Bethlehem (The Bread House in literal translation) needs special commentary. Bethlehem is a city south of Jerusalem, on the border of the Judean Desert, mentioned in the Book of Ruth that is read in synagogue on the Shavuot holiday which describes how Naomi from the Elimelech family and her daughter-in-law Ruth turned on widowed and destitute. Naomi decides to return to Bethlehem and her daughter-in-law Ruth goes with her, and they live as widows in Bethlehem. Eventually, Ruth becomes the great-grandmother of King David the greatest king in the history of Israel who moved the capital of Israel to Jerusalem (מגילת רות). This city is also mentioned in the New Testament and the Church of the Nativity located now in Bethlehem was built on the hill which in Christian beliefs is the birthplace of Jesus. The Old Testament (the first division of the Christian biblical canon, based primarily upon the Tanakh, or Hebrew Bible - Bandstra, 2004), together with the New Testament (collection of Christian texts originally written in the Koine Greek language and discusses Jesus, and early Christianity - Jones, 2000) is a Christian Bible, considered holy scripture by Christians.

The well-known and widespread metaphor a land flowing with milk and honey (land of milk and honey), *ארץ זבת חלב ודבש* is a Tanakh metaphorical name of the Land of Israel, the Promised Land, in which the Almighty promised to lead the Jewish people, with a hyperbolic description of its richness, abundance, and fertility (Cohen).

About two years after the Israelites left Egypt and wandered in the wilderness, Moses prepared to enter the land of Canaan and sent a leader from each tribe to inspect this land. After forty days, spies returned to the Israelites in the desert, and eight men carried a very large grape bunch on a pole. "And they said: We have come to the land to which you sent us and it flowing with milk and honey." The modern extension of this metaphor means abundance, prosperity, and serenity, and has even a humoristic connotation: unattainable carefree life.

The idioms *לא חלב, לא בשר* (without a clear character) and *milk toast* (a meek, submissive, or timid) are personal characteristics and partial semantic equivalents in meaning, lexica, and syntax.

Hebrew and English Ethnocultural Bread and Milk Metaphors

Ethnocultural metaphors result from different living environments, material, and spiritual cultures, thinking modes, and the values of the culture itself (Gannon, 2002: 3).

המוציא לחם מן הארץ (the one who brings bread out of the land) is a blessing that religious Jewish tell until eating (Ben Ami, 2015). Generally, this complicated global metaphor consisted of some small metaphors is an expression of deep gratitude for the food for a living, which makes it possible to function, it is a recognition that food, the human body, and the land are given by the hands of the creator and under his care. Brings bread is a metaphor for the Creator, bread is a symbol of food, and bread out of the land is a symbol of the complicated bread production process that begins from wheat cultivation and depends on nature (Creator).

לחם העוני (the bread of poverty, *matzah*) is unleavened bread eaten on the days of the Passover holiday.

Since the Israelites left Egypt in a big hurry, the bread dough did not have time to rise and they ate matzah, processed from only two ingredients - flour and water. Matzah eating for seven days is a symbolic reminder of the exodus from Egyptian slavery and the transition to a free life.

The Tanakh proverb *עובד אדמתו ישבע לחם* (works his land will be fed bread) is the conceptual metaphor for the results of human efforts: to enjoy the fruits of his work is promised to the farmer who cared for his field, seedlings, plantings, watering. Hebrew bread conception is in line with these ones in other languages (Monteiro et al., 2018; Yurina & Pomarolli, 2017).

Milk metaphors in Hebrew are connected to pleasure, enjoyment (*ארץ זבת חלב ודבש*, land of milk and honey), and also with youngness, inexperience (*יש לו חלב על השפתיים*, he has milk on his lips; *טיפת חלב*, a drop of milk, child, the mother, and the family consultation).

Table 2a.

Hebrew Ethnocultural Bread and Milk Metaphors

	<i>המוציא לחם מן הארץ תהלים</i>
<i>The one who brings bread out of the land</i> One of the most important and famous blessings is exempt from other blessings, but its obligation cannot be canceled by another blessing.	
<i>Works his land will be fed bread</i> Guaranteed the fruits of the man invested his efforts, the means to advance any cause	<i>עובד אדמתו ישבע לחם משלי יב, פסוק יא</i>
<i>Poor bread</i> A matzah pastry eaten on Seder night, Judaism	<i>לחם העוני דברים טז, ג</i>
<i>The outside bread</i> A total of twelve challahs made of semolina were placed in two sets on the table.	<i>לחם הפנים פרשת תרומה שבספר שמות</i>
Basic livelihood, sufficient for a person's living; an essential permanent thing	<i>לחם חוק השולחן ערוך / כבוד מלך</i>
A person who utters good, pleasant things, it's fun to hear them.	<i>דבש וחלב תחת לשונו שיר השירים ד יא</i>
<i>Milk slot</i> Cheese block	<i>חריץ חלב</i>
<i>He has milk on his lips</i> Youngness, inexperience	<i>יש לו חלב על השפתיים</i>
<i>A milk drop</i> a network of medical consultation points for the health of the child, the mother and the family	<i>טיפת חלב</i>

English Ethnocultural Bread and Milk Metaphors

In two languages, exist the connection of bread as a symbol of food and life - human existence - the Creator. While the blessing (*המוציא לחם מן הארץ* the one that brings the bread) is the gratitude of the eater to the Creator, in Christian prayer, Jesus himself begs from Lord "Give us this day our daily bread" (Matthew 6:11; Luke 11:3).

This important English bread metaphor and a number of others (*holy bread; bread and wine; I have broken the staff of your bread*) are connected to the Christian Bible. Holy bread, sacramental bread, and communion bread are metaphors of Jesus's body and blood used in the Eucharist Christian ritual that is linked to the Last Supper (Eucharist) when Jesus

blessed bread, broke it, and said to the disciples "Take, eat; this is My body" (Matthew 26:17–29). The metaphor to break the staff of your bread, to break bread is a symbol of welcome, of openness, a gesture signifying peace (Leviticus 26:70) and its modern nonreligious expansion - have a meal, eat, friendliness and informality.

In many English metaphors bread is a concept of living, wellness, and money (*breadwinner; bring home bread and butter, heavy bread*) and the absence of bread means poverty (below the breadline, take the bread out from people's mouths).

We found the source domain and the target domains:

bread - hospitality (*a bread-and-butter letter*);

bread - advantages, benefits(*to have bread buttered on both sides; know on which side your bread is buttered; bread always falls on the buttered side* (pessimistic connotation); the best thing since sliced bread).

An unexpected source of the idiom *breadcrumb navigation* or a list of items used as navigation aids on a computer interface is a German fairy tale about Hansel and Gretel, in which the eponymous characters came back home on a trail of breadcrumbs.

Shakespeare's expression of 16th century *milk of human kindness* (kindness, compassion) is the only

milk metaphor with meliorative connotation and the rest are exceptionally negative:

milk - not practical (*it's no good/use crying over spilled milk; milk the bull / the pigeon/ the ram /a duck, milk dry*).

milk - uncomfortable (*be like a fly in milk*);

milk - tasteless, contentless (*milk and water*);

milk – dishonest (*to bring home the milk*), its an antonym to bring home bread and butter that has a positive connotation.

Table 2b.

English Ethnocultural Bread and Milk Metaphors

<i>daily bread</i> the petition Lord's Prayer from "Give us this day our daily bread" (Matthew 6:11) or "Give us day by day our daily bread" (Luke 11:3) The modern extension: living, food, and money.
<i>holy bread</i> sacramental bread, communion bread, and sacramental wine is used in the Eucharist Christian ritual to represent Jesus's body and blood
<i>to break bread</i> In the Last Supper Jesus said to the disciples "Take, eat; this is My body" after the blessing and breaking some bread (Matthew 26:17–29).
The modern extension: have a meal, eat, friendliness and informality
<i>to break the staff of your bread</i> to destroy the staff or the support which bread is to man (Leviticus 26:70)
<i>below the breadline</i> the poverty line
<i>breadwinner</i> main earner in a family
<i>bread and butter</i> main income, livelihood
<i>take the bread out from people's mouth</i> to deprive someone of money, wealth
<i>have bread buttered on both sides</i> to receive two separate benefits or advantages
<i>know on which side your bread is buttered</i> to understand what is to your benefit
<i>bread basket</i> an agricultural area where wheat etc. is grown
<i>bread money</i> , slang
<i>heavy bread</i> lot of money, slang
<i>the best thing since sliced bread</i> very good, useful how great something
<i>a bread-and-butter letter</i> a short, hand-written communication to thank someone who has recently provided the writer with hospitality, usually dinner or an overnight visit
<i>breadcrumb trail</i> a list of items used as navigation aids on a computer interface)
<i>milk of human kindness</i> compassion, empathy
<i>bring home the milk</i> disrespect on oneself
<i>milk and water</i> tasteless, faceless, contentless, foodless, inexpressive symbolizes dilution (weak, sentimental suggestions or ideas something valuable, possessing, low quality
<i>milk the bull / the pigeon/ the ram /a duck</i> to do something pointless or futile, old-fashioned
<i>milk dry</i> to try to get as much as possible from a person, thing, or situation
<i>be like a fly in milk</i> uncomfortable feeling

Conclusion

The investigation of English and Hebrew bread metaphors confirms its value as a meta-conceptual metaphor because of its numerous symbolic meanings while the key meaning of bread is - the most urgent physical person's needs as food for life. Bread is a dichotomy symbol of wealth, plenty that is opposite to hunger, poverty and in a modern extension, bread symbolizes a person that provides for the family, and made money.

The sources of English and Hebrew Bread and Milk metaphors are diverse (Rome satire, Greek Mythology, French phrase, German fairytale) but Tanakh and the New Testament are the eldest and most important sources of equivalent and ethnocultural ones. While Tanakh and Biblical Metaphors featured philosophical meaning, and a high level of symbolization and conceptualization, the late metaphors characterized practical, pragmatical, or even cynic connotations. We

found the Hebrew metaphor *הַמְּבִיא לֶחֶם מִן הָאָרֶץ* (*The one who brings bread out of the land*) which is a complex number of metaphors and in such a way it express complicated universal meaning and two English metaphors featured antonym connection(*to bring home bread and butter - to bring home milk*).

This limited study found a range of equivalent and non-equivalent figurative meanings across the two languages. Hebrew milk metaphors are the concept of pleasure and enjoyment, especially when combined with honey, while English ones featured negative connotations and the inferior status of milk in opposition to bread.

Ethnocultural figurative language did not paint a picture of freely forming networks of meanings in any of the languages that cannot be organized in microsystems as already did with color idioms in two languages (Kigel, 2022).

Future directions are investigating cake and honey as English and Hebrew food metaphors, general attitudes to food and drink, and bread and milk metaphors in more languages.

References

1. Gannon, M. (2002) Cultural metaphors: Their use in management practice and as a method for understanding cultures. In W. J. Lonner, D. L. Dinnel, S. A. Hayes, & D. N. Sattler (Eds.), *Online Readings in Psychology and Culture*, Unit 16, Chapter 4. Pp.1-10. <http://www.wvu.edu/~culture>
2. Newman, J.(1997.) *Eating and Drinking as Sources of Metaphor in English*. *Cuadernos de Filología Inglesa* 6, 2: 213-231.
3. Korthals, M. (2008. ") *Food as a Source and Target of Metaphors: Inclusion and Exclusion of Food-stuffs and Persons through Metaphors.*". *Configurations*, vol. 16 no. 1, p. 77-92. *Project MUSE*, doi:10.1353/con.0.0044.
4. Kay C. (2016) *Food as a fruitful source of metaphor.* Pp. 66–78. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198744573.003.0005>
5. Arasaratnam, L. (2013) *Intercultural communication competence*. In A. Kurylo (Ed.), *Intercultural communication: Representation and construction of culture* (Chap 3, pp. 47-68). Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications.
6. Littlemore, J. and Low, G. (2006) *Metaphoric Competence and Communicative Language Ability*. *Applied Linguistics*, 27, 268-294. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/aml004>
7. *Figure of speech*. Merriam-Webster Dictionary. Merriam-Webster, Inc. 2015.
8. *Definition of Metaphor*. www.merriam-webster.com. Access 1.12.22.
9. Lakoff, G., and Johnson, M. (1980) *Metaphors We Live By*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
10. *Ethnolinguistics*. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Access 1.12.22.
11. Piirainen E. (2012) *Widespread Idioms in Europe and Beyond. Toward a Lexicon of Common Figurative Units*. *Monographs*, P.591. DOI 10.3726/978-1-4539-0845-7.
12. Pinnavaia, L. (2010) *Sugar and Spice... Exploring Food and Drink Idioms in English*. *Polimetrica International Scientific Publisher Monza/Italy*. Pp 361.
13. Pinnavaia, L.(2015) *We are what we eat: Analyzing food and drink idioms in English, French, German, and Spanish*. Pp. 465-469.
14. Pinnavaia, L.(2018) *Food and Drink Idioms in English: "A little bit more sugar and lots of spice"*. *Cambridge Scholars Publishing*, Pp. 235.
15. Pomarolli G. (2021) *Cultural-Specific and Universal Components of the Russian Food Metaphor in Comparative, Linguistic, Cultural and Lexicographic Aspects*, National Research Tomsk State University.
16. Ye, Z. (2010) *Eating and Drinking in Mandarin and Shanghainese: A Lexical-Conceptual Analysis*. In *Proceedings of the 9th Conference of the Australasian Society for Cognitive Science*, 375-383.
17. Martins C.(2015) *Water in your mouth - Food metaphors in the Portuguese language*. *Teaching Crossroads*. 10th Erasmus Week.
18. Moore, T. (2017) *Food and Life: Metaphors from Kitchen and Table in Brazil*", *PLData* [quarterly newsletter of the Portuguese Language Division of the ATA], Vol. 15, no. 2 (Oct. 2006), p. 8-9.
19. Ionescu, D. (2017). *Food Idioms and Proverbs in English and Romanian – A Crosslinguistic and Cross-cultural Approach*. Bucharest: OSCAR Print.
20. Majić K.(2017) *Idiomatic expressions associated with the domain FOOD in English and their counterparts in Croatian Osijek*. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/197875329.pdf>.
21. Negro I. (2019) *Metaphor and Metonymy in Food Idioms*. *Languages*, 4(3), 47; <https://doi.org/10.3390/languages4030047>
22. Kigel T. (2022a) *Contrastive analysis of English, Russian and Hebrew Color Idioms*. *European Journal of Literature, Language and Linguistics Studies* – V, 6, Is. 2, 2022. Pp.39-52. DOI 10.46827/ejll.v6i2.374
23. Kigel T. (2022b) *English and Hebrew metaphors with an edible plant(furthering)*.
24. Yurina E., Avramenko O., Pomarolli G. (2017) *THE IMAGES OF GRAIN AND BREAD IN RUSSIAN, ENGLISH AND ITALIAN LANGUAGES: UNIVERSAL ASPECTS OF METAPHORIZATION*. *Tomsk State Pedagogical University Bulletin Issue 11 (188)* Pp. 135-139. DOI:1023951/1609-624X-2017-11-135-139
25. Yurina E., Pomarolli, G. (2017) *The biblical symbolism of bread in figurative means of Russian and Italian languages*, 84-106. DOI - 10.17223/19996195/39/6
26. *Bread: THE MOST IMPORTANT THING IN HUMAN HISTORY* <https://grantsbakery.co.uk/blogs/posts/bread-the-most-important-thing-in-human-history>.
27. Van Winckel, M., Velde, S., De Bruyne, R., Van Biervliet, S. (2011). "Clinical Practice". *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 170 (12): 1489–1494.
28. *Milky Way Galaxy: Facts About Our Galactic Home* (2017) *Space.com*.
29. Carr, D. (2011). *The Formation of the Hebrew Bible: A New Reconstruction*, p. 342. Oxford University Press.
30. Tov, E. (2008). *Hebrew Bible, Greek Bible, and Qumran*. Mohr Siebeck. doi:10.1628/978-3-16-151454-8.
31. Ledwon D. (2017) *Bread and Water as Metaphors for the Word of God in the Four Gospels*. *Ruch Biblijny i Liturgiczny*, 70: 2. Pp. 109–135. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21906/rbl.287>
32. Bandstra, B. (2004) *Reading the Old Testament: an introduction to the Hebrew Bible*, Wadsworth.
33. Jones, B. (2000) *Canon of the Old Testament*, *Dictionary of the Bible*, William B. Eerdmans.
34. Cohen J. *WHY MILK AND HONEY* <https://www.jonathancohenweb.com/m&h.html> Access 1.12.22.

35. Ben Ami D. (2015) Metaphors in the Torah: "The Land of Milk and Honey". The Jerusalem Post. Access 1.12.22.

36. Eucharist. Encyclopædia Britannica. Britannica.com. Access 1.12.22 Eucharist. Encyclopædia Britannica. Britannica.com. Access 1.12.22

37.

ממלכתי State Bible אתר תנ"ך מלכתני Tanakh website.

<https://edu.929.org.il/enrichment/%D7%91%D7%99%D7%AA-%D7%9C%D7%97%D7%9D/>

38.

תנ"ך: פורטל מגילת רוח
<https://he.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D7%A4%D7%95%D7%A8%D7%98%D7%9C:%D7%AA%D7%A0%22%D7%A>

39. Old and New Testament. OFFICIAL KING JAMES BIBLE ONLINE. <https://www.kingjamesbibleonline.org/>

40. (Wikimilon)

ויקימילון

<https://www.google.com/search?q=%D7%95%D7%99%D7%A7%D7%99%D7%9E%D7%99%D7%9C%D7%95%D7%9F&aq=%D7%95%D7%99%D7%A7%D7%99%D7%9E%D7%99%D7%9C%D7%95%D7%9F&aq=chrome.0.69i5914j69i6113.1690j0j7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8>

41. מילון עברי-עברי <https://milog.co.il>

42. Idioms and Phrases. The Free Dictionary <https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com/>

43. Merriam Webster Dictionary. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/>

ENGLISH AND HEBREW METAPHORS WITH EDIBLE PLANT NAMES

Kigel T.

Independent researcher of multilingualism (Project "Contrastive Analysis of English, Hebrew and Russian Color Idioms"), author of about 30 published academic papers.

Research interests - multilingualism, translation,

teaching a second language and mathematics, learning disabilities

The author of the books and textbooks: "שעשועי גיאמטריה", "99 משחקי תנועה וחברה", "מוכנים ומזומנים לכיתה א'".

Orcid <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4136-4711>

Behazlaha-center, Petah-Tikva, Israel

Abstract

The aim of the work is to study English and Jewish figurative language with the names of edible plants and culinary motivation from an interlingual and intercultural perspective. For the first time, we offer a systematic lexicographic description of this layer of Food metaphors, including the identification, analysis, and classification. The result of the corpus of 119 metaphors systematization (75 English and 44 Hebrew, are English and Hebrew tables with names of edible plants, biblical and widespread, full, partial equivalents, and ethnocultural metaphors. In quantitative terms English metaphors predominate over Hebrew ones, the English list of plant names is more extensive, although there are exclusive plants both in the English and Hebrew list. This study focuses on conceptual metaphors, linguacultural comments, lexical and semantic characteristics, similarities, and differences in English and Hebrew figurative language.

Keywords: food metaphor, conceptual metaphor, edible plants, figurative language, English, Hebrew, cross-linguistic perspective.

1. Introduction Metaphors with Edible Plants1. Introduction

Food is a universal human need and Food metaphors (a poetically or rhetorically ambitious use of words, a figurative, as opposed to literal use, Metaphor) are very productive in modern discourses because they are "a mirror of a linguistic community's historical, social, political, and cultural story"(Pinnavaia, 2015: 455). The names of botanical crops as highly productive edible plants such as trees, shrubs, and herbs, are semantic models of figurative language (Pamies, et al, 2015). Due to the fact that individuals and societies denote their ethnic, national, social, class, gender, and linguistic identity through food figurative language(Metaphor, FOOD A) metaphors are very important for multicultural communication as a symbolic, interpretive, transactional, contextual process, in which people from different cultures create shared meanings. (Lustig & Koester, 2007:46). Metaphoric Competence is acquired in second language learning and teaching as a part of

grammatical, textual sociolinguistic competence (Littlemore& Low, 2006:268).

The theoretical base of this work is Lakoff's theory concern the conceptual metaphor as a universal process of human thinking reflected in language structures and leads to the interaction of two cognitive structures or areas: the source domain and the target domain with complicated links between them (Lakoff, 1980)- and the ideas on the metaphor cultural dependence and the multilingual approach (Dobrovolsky& Pirainen, 2005; Piirainen, 2012:62).

In recent decades, a large number of linguistic research focuses on phraseology or figurative language (a set of set expressions), and, in particular, Food concepts and metaphors in different languages. An important contribution to food metaphors studies contributed books and studies on food Metaphors in English(Pinnavaia, 2018), Portuguese (Monteiro, 2011), Spanish (Pamies, 2011, 2014); and Russian (Pomarolli, 2021).